

The *kribit* method of raising seedlings

Abdur Rashid Gomosta, senior scientific officer, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

In the *kribit* (Bengali: artificial seedbed) method of raising seedlings, light competition is encouraged in a primary seedbed and discouraged in a secondary bed. The *kribit* method is of two types: 1) the *kribit* stripping method (KSM), and 2) the *kribit* transplanting method (KTM).

The primary bed is a clay soil substratum (3–4 cm thick) on banana leaves or polyethylene sheets. Decomposed organic matter (25% by volume) and NPK (20-20-20 kg/ha) are

mixed with the soil. Seeds having 80% viability are soaked for 24 hours and incubated for 48 hours, then sown on the substratum at the rate of 1 kg/sq m and covered with well-dried straw measuring 20–50 cm long. Water is sprayed on the straw immediately, then once a day during humid weather or twice a day during dry weather. On the fourth day after sowing, the straw is removed; the seedlings turn green within 12 hours.

In KSM, the primary bed is divided into strips 6–10 cm wide and 1 meter long on the fifth day after sowing. The strips are placed 6–10 cm apart in the secondary bed, which is made of

puddled soil, and fertilized with urea at 6–100 g/sq m. In KTM, seedlings are transplanted in bunches of 30 to 40 on the seventh day. They are then well irrigated for 1 to 3 weeks. The secondary bed is twice the size of the primary.

Two-week-old *kribit* seedlings produce double the dry matter of 2-week-old modified *dapog* seedlings; they are also greener and stiffer. Three- or four-week-old *kribit* seedlings are similar to or sometimes better than wetbed seedlings. They are transplanted from the secondary bed, two or three seedlings to the hill.

Machinery development & testing

Modification of dusters by Thai farmers

Vichai Khusakul and Raywat Pattarasudhi, Division of Entomology and Zoology, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok 9, Thailand

The use of granular insecticides against brown planthoppers is not practical where the water is more than 12 cm deep because the water dilutes the insecticide.

Farmers in Narapiron district, Nakornpathom province, Thailand, in 1974 found that they could not control the planthoppers even with the most effective dusts. Since brown planthoppers produce their progeny near the water level, and most rice varieties used by the farmers are the high-tillering, dwarf types, good penetration by dust insecticides at maximum tillering is not possible. The farmers have found an easy, rapid, and inexpensive solution.

One end of a small aluminum beer can or tin can is removed; near the other end, two smooth holes about 2 cm in diameter are bored opposite each other on the sides of the can. The can is then fitted firmly to the duster hose (Fig. 1a).

Beer can modified by Thai farmers (a) and fitted firmly over end of duster hose can reach several rows of rice plants with a low, horizontally spreading pattern (b).

The duster fan forces insecticide through the horizontal holes, covering several rows of rice (Fig. 1b) in two directions. Farmers save dusting time

and are better able to control insecticide placement. The amount of insecticide is also reduced and there is less danger of oral and inhalation toxicity.